

Average weekly catches of predators of rice pests in light traps of different colors. IRRI, 1988.

Selected predators caught in different color light traps. IRRI, 1988.

Color	Visible light wavelength range (Å) ^a	Insects (no.)/trap per night ^b			
		<i>Microvelia</i> sp.	<i>Opus</i> sp.	<i>Cyrtorhinus</i> sp.	Formicidae
Ultraviolet	4400-7300	10.31 bc	7.07 b	3.75 c	39.39 b
Violet	4000-5700	5.12 cd	4.81 bc	3.40 d	24.59 cd
Blue	4400-5500	6.71 cd	4.46 c	1.71 de	21.99 c
Green	4700-6500	9.00 c	8.30 bc	4.21 c	57.34 b
Yellow	5200-6900	14.86 b	9.52 bc	7.18 b	78.72 b
Orange	5600-6700	4.94 d	1.54 d	1.04 de	25.58 d
Red	4300-7300	3.91 d	1.15 d	1.01 e	21.05 cd
White	4100-6300	30.64 a	13.04 a	26.66 a	109.81 a

^a Measurements done using a Welch Spectroscope. ^b Av of catches over a 10-wk period. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Pheromone components of rice leaffolders (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia patnalis*

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We measured electroantennogram responses of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* to 20 pheromone standards. Ten µl of 5

mg/ml solutions of each pheromone standard were applied on filter paper and allowed to evaporate for 1 min to remove the solvent.

Responses of males of both species to these stimuli were higher for Z11-16:Ac and Z13-18:Ac (Fig. 1). Female moths did not respond.

Dose-response curves indicate that *M. patnalis* is more sensitive to Z13-18:Ac; *C. medinalis* is more sensitive to Z11-

16:Ac (Fig. 2). Z13-18:Ac was positively identified in the pheromone gland extracts of *M. patnalis*.

It appears that both species use both compounds in their pheromone blends. Species isolation is maintained because of different ratios of the compounds in the pheromone blends.

Based on the EAG responses and the GC-MS analysis of crude extracts of *M. patnalis* pheromone glands, the ratio of Z13-18:Ac and Z11-16:Ac was tenta-

Absolute EAG amplitude (-MV)

1. Electroantennogram responses of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* to pheromone standards. * Indicates a significant higher response.

Integrated pest management – other pests

Correlation between *Hirschmanniella oryzae* population and rice grain weight

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We collected 20 plant samples of rice variety RD10 at ripening randomly from the experimental field in 1989 wet season. The number of rice root nematodes *Hirschmanniella oryzae* extracted from roots was compared with grain weight of each sample.

The correlation coefficient between number of nematodes in 1 g root with 100-grain weight was -0.677. The regression analysis of a linear model for the number of nematodes in roots (X) and 100-grain weight (Y) was $Y = 2.942 - 0.002X$ (see figure).

We also compared the nematode population in 1 g root with plant height. The correlation coefficient was not significant. ■

% EAG relative to standard (1-hexanol)

2. Dose response curves of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* for Z13-18:Ac and Z11-16:Ac.

tively fixed at 96:4 for *M. patnalis* and 2:98 for *C. medinalis*.

Further analysis of a larger number of pheromone gland extracts and behavioral

studies with different ratios of the two compounds are needed to determine the blend that is most effective for monitoring the two LF species. ■

Estimated regression of grain weight of RD10 because of *Hirschmanniella oryzae* population under field conditions at Pathumthani Rice Research Center, 1989. ** = significant at the 1% level.